

Can Workplace Design enhance creativity and adaptation to change?

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Abstract

Our work examines the role of workplace design as an enabler of creative innovative work. We assume that competitive pressures to innovate and adapt to changes create a stressful reality accompanied by negative emotions for many employees. We argue that while such emotions have to be managed in order to achieve organizational goals, management often fails to provide effective and satisfactory solutions in this area. We therefore ask if workplace design can enable this ‘emotion management’ challenge and consequently enhance creativity and adaptation to change.

Building on the design literature that sees design as tasked with creating contexts for positive experiences we offer a preliminary insight into the ways by which workplace design can generate such context acting as a persuasive artifact that invites people to engage by stimulating their interest and imagination and facilitating and accommodating their contributions. More specifically, we examine the potency of color as a design lever to eliciting desired individual emotions.

While we peel off the outer layer of the ‘design as a creator of context for positive experience’ phenomenon, we conclude that additional research is needed to further reinforce the notion of design as a creator of desired context for experience and identify the means and levers by which such aim is achieved.

Managing emotions through workplace design

Most if not all of the competitive companies operating today are exposed to increasing competitive pressures and the concurrent need to differentiate and adapt. These pressures aren't just felt in boardrooms but instead they are shared by employees who are expected to work more creatively, collaboratively and effectively than ever before. Evidently the emotional undercurrentsⁱ of change have a profound impact on individual behavior within organizations. Even though organizations undergoing transformation espouse positive pro-change rhetoric, they are rarely effective in addressing the naturally triggered negative emotions of fear and anxiety that often accompany organizational change (Middleton, 1989). The continuous pressure to innovate and differentiate adds tremendous stress to employees' lives (Friedman, 2004). And as Fineman (1993) so aptly points out, too often organizations fail to nourish people's psyche and ignore their emotional needs.

Managing emotions, especially negative ones, is no small task. Change literature focuses on the 'recipients of change' (Jick, 1993) assuming simplistically that management knows how to treat defense, denial, and anger. In reality as the literature on Emotional IQ suggests, managers have substantial limitations when attempting to effectively manage people's emotions. For example, research by the Center for Creative Leadership found that the primary cause of derailment in executives involve their deficits in emotional competence. The three primary causes identified were: difficulty in handling change, not being able to work well in a team, and poor interpersonal relationsⁱⁱ. Perhaps it is not realistic to expect managers to effectively manage individual emotions?

Our examination of the potential of workplace design to create a context of positive emotions to counter challenging emotions associated with creativity and change builds off contemporary thinking in the field of design that views *designing* as a *possibility-creating activity* focused on the *relationship* between the user and the design (be it designed products, objects or environments) and the subsequent desired *experience* that is created (Hekkert, 2001). According to this view design shifts from creating products to creating *contexts for experience* where the user is seduced to experience the designed object or reality with all his or her senses (Overbeeke et al., 1999). By designing *contexts for*

experience instead of products, objects and/or environments the focus shifts from the result of interaction towards the involvement *in and during* interaction (Hummels, 1999). This person-design interactive experience is *affective* in nature and involves a great variety of emotionsⁱⁱⁱ.

By focusing on how organizational members experience the work space they inhabit, workplace design may create a context for desired emotional experience that supports people in enhancing their creativity and better manage organizational change goals.

What is the role that emotion should play in our approaches to design? “How do we design for emotion?” Good question, but it implies that one can identify emotion as a design target, then craft an artifact (an application, a device, a thing, for example) that meets this target.

Don Norman, Symposium on Foundations of Interaction Design, 2003

But how is the potential to create a context for positive experience unleashed? How is a desired emotional experience generated through workplace design? Desmet & Hekkert (2001) argued that of all affective states or experiences, the emotional experience is the most relevant for understanding product (or designed) experience because only *emotions* imply a one-to-one relationship between the experience and the object. If a design looks or performs in a way that corresponds with a concern of the individual, a pleasant emotional response will result and conversely, if it conflicts, the emotion will be unpleasant. Designs evoke emotions when they are perceived to touch upon individuals’ concerns or preference (Frijda, 1986; Reeves & Nass, 1996).

As design creates a context for experience for individuals who interact with that design^{iv}, the resultant emotions may enable or hinder adaptation to change. Framing the connection between positive emotions and adaptation to change Fredrickson (2000) develops an insightful argument emphasizing the significant role of positive emotions (specified in Fredrickson’s research as joy, contentment and interest^v) in broadening a person’s thought-action repertoire and building that individual’s enduring personal resources. It is these same personal resources that served the ancestral function of promoting survival. Fredrickson provides a detailed account of the relationship that exists between negative

emotions and the narrowing of one's thought process and action repertoire. In contrast, she points out that positive emotions may improve the ability to generate creative thought, develop relationship with others, and over all perform at a higher level. Lastly, Fredrickson proposes that positive emotions have an undoing effect on negative emotions. That is, positive emotions can counter the negative emotions associated with change and may enable creative thought which is critical to the ability to learn and effectively cope with change.

Supporting Fredrickson, Norman (2002) argues that positive affect enhances creative and breadth-first thinking, whereas negative emotions focus on cognition, enhancing depth-first processing and minimizing distractions. Therefore, Norman continues, it is essential that products/objects designed for use under stress follow good human-centered design, for stress makes people less able to cope with difficulties and less flexible in their approach to problem solving. Instead, positive affect makes people more tolerant of minor difficulties and more flexible and creative in finding solutions. Thus, Norman concludes, just as negative affect can make some simple tasks difficult, positive affect can make some difficult tasks easier, and both affects can be triggered and/or facilitated by design.

Furthermore, Isen (1993) also showed that the positive affective system changes the cognitive parameters of problem solving to emphasize breadth-first thinking, and the examination of multiple solutions and courses of action. Conversely, anxiety has just the opposite effect: it biases the processing to be depth first, focused, concentrated and overall it narrows the thought process. In general, negative affect enables focus upon a specific threat or problem, but it prevents the adaptive and creative problem solving that is usually required under conditions of change and uncertainty (Mills and Kleinman, 1988). Evidently, the relationship between positive emotions and adaptation to change appears powerful, and the thought that such association can be triggered by designing workplaces that serve as context for positive experience is of even greater interest. Cupchik notes:

Design also has an aesthetic side to the extent that the form of tools or images embody sensory qualities that shape experience and are related to each other in a coherent manner. This is a bottom-

up process in which sensation is valued in and of itself (i.e. intrinsically) and not because it conveys information related to the practical (i.e. extrinsic) use of the instrument.” (p.5)

And so, if emotions can be influenced by the deliberate design of contexts for experience^{vi}, what particular levers can designers employ to carefully structure the desired positive emotional experience? Workplace design theory offers very little insight into how such positive experience is created. Indeed, designing a positive context of experience is assumed as a non-trivial challenge.

Leveraging color to create a context for positive experience

Looking into design levers at a designer’s disposal we note key levers such as point/line, form/shape/space, movement, color, pattern and texture (Pile, 1988). Of these six design levers, we ask if any one stands out as the lever more effective at engaging individuals and impacting emotions. Researchers suggest that color is a strong lever and that color provides the fastest track to emotions (Baker, 2004). Those who do not share this view, such as Willats (2004), who suggests that shape is more important than color, still acknowledge that other design levers, shape included, lack the expressive vocabulary that color enjoys, as well the stronger research-base for understanding colors’ association to emotions. Willats says:

Shape and color are two key factors in design, and in order to think and talk about the shape and color of a product during the course of the design process effective ways of describing both are needed. A comprehensive vocabulary for describing color is available and there is a well-established link between color and the emotions. But what words can be used to describe shape, and are there particular emotional responses to different kinds of shapes? (p.180)

Research on color and emotion began as early as the late 1800s (Fehrman & Fehrman, 2004). Researchers at that time thought that the emotional connection to color could be one means to understand individuals’ preferences. Early studies centered on determining exact color emotion connections using a defined color set, for example red, yellow, blue, green, and a defined emotion set, for example anger, joy, happy, and sad. Studies varied greatly in size with a range of 6 to 48 emotions per set. More recent studies have tried to

reduce the large numbers of color-emotion scales to smaller groups in an attempt to facilitate comparisons across studies (for example the work of Kwallek et al., 1996).

Over the years, color studies have grown to include a wide range of contexts including pharmaceutical (Formosa, 2004), lighting (Mead, 2004), materials (Mottram, 2004; Zuo, Hope, Jones, & Castle, 2004) and textiles in relationship to office furniture (Mottram, 2004). Perhaps the most relevant contemporary work today is that of Mahnke (1996) and Mahnke & Mahnke (1993), which specifically address color-emotion associations within the workplace. Let us explore in greater detail, the power of color as a design lever.

Searching for design levers that promote positive affect Mahnke (1996) discusses, in great detail, the affect of *color* and light in designed environments on the inhabitants' emotional well-being. Mahnke presents his and others' color-emotion association studies^{vii} and points to the significant relationship between specific colors and specific emotions. For example, his summarizing discussion of the color Gray suggests that:

Pure Gray is conservative, quiet, and calm, but also dreary, tedious, passive and without life...in the Gray zone there is no clarity in any direction – it is neutral...Gray lacks energy; it has no will of its own. It does not want to get involved and make any definite statement. In color design it takes on the characteristic of the adjacent color (p.66)

Yellow however enjoys a very different set of characteristics:

Reflective and luminous, Yellow is the happiest of all colors. In its positive associations and impressions it is cheerful, high-spirited, and suggestive of the life-giving sun. It represents a bright future, hope, wisdom and it is expansive -not earthbound... Yellow is used in packaging and advertising to express activity and cheerfulness (p.67)

While Yellow is associated with happiness, Gray is correlated with mourning and sorrow across a number of studies. Why, then, are the offices of the corporate world so heavily decorated with Gray? What affective experience is created by totally 'Gray-ing' cubical walls and office furniture^{viii}? While we can intuitively gage the answer to such a question, not much empirical knowledge has been developed in this area thus far:

Less research has evaluated the indirect impact of environments of different colors when individuals are working on specific tasks as opposed to viewing or observing the environmental color (Stone, 2003, p.65)

Research shows that persons subjected to under-stimulation exhibited symptoms of restlessness, excessive emotional response, difficulty in concentration, irritation, and in some cases, a variety of more extreme reactions (Mahnke and Mahnke, 1993). At the same time, totally 'de-Gray-ing' the workplace may not be the solution either. Kuller collected measurements during the 1st, 2nd and 3rd hours of exposure to a multi-color environment and found that subjects generally experienced a lack of emotional control in a colorful room. Subjects EKG (heart rate) was slower in the colorful room than in the Gray one, which is in agreement with a hypothesis of other researchers (in Lacey et al., 1963) that intense attention might be accompanied by cardiac deceleration. Mahnke and Mahnke write:

It is especially interesting to note that brain-wave activity was lower in the colorful room than in the gray room and the heart response was slower in the colorful room. Therefore, we may conclude that a dull environment tends to prod brain activity, which may induce anxiety, fear and distress (1993, p.6).

The importance of color was recognized in a survey by Avery Office Products in the UK in 2004^{ix}. This survey found that over 60% of British businesses believe they can improve staff morale and motivation by adding color to their work environment. Specifically, the survey found that only 11% of the 1000 office workers surveyed 'enjoyed' working in cream, beige, or brown office environments, when 38% of offices feature these colors. Of the respondents, 88% claimed more vibrant colors would improve morale, efficiency, and performance. More specifically, 20% would prefer light blue, 13% would select light green, and 16% would prefer yellow to increase their morale and overall performance. All of the respondents preferred colors somehow linked to nature and renewal. While these results are clearly important in the support they provide to color design decisions, very little of the 'intuition' recorded in this study is backed by empirical research. In fact, when looking at Kwallek et al.'s findings (1996) the picture is further complicated.

These researchers studied the impact of interior office color schemes on employees' mood and performance. Six-hundred and seventy-five subjects were asked to perform clerical work, like proofreading, while situated in offices painted with different colors. Findings from the study suggest that overall subjects made significantly more errors when working

in a white office than in red and blue offices^x. Gender differences were also noted whereby females performed significantly better than males irrespective of office color but also experienced more depression, confusion, and anger when working in white, gray, or beige offices. Males, on the other hand, reported greater depression confusion and anger in high saturated office color (green, blue, purple, red, yellow, and orange). Interestingly, when asked, subjects preferred working in beige and white offices and were not interested in working in orange and purple color offices.

In a consecutive study Kwallek et al. (1997) tested 90 workers' mood and productivity in three office color schemes including bright red, light blue-green and white. Subjects were randomly assigned to one of the three offices and were asked to perform a variety of office tasks throughout a four-day-eight-hour workweek. Performance results and mood were carefully monitored. Results showed no difference in mood and/or performance level for subjects assigned to different color office. Only when researchers factored in pre-screened individual differences in ability to screen irrelevant environmental stimuli, did color mattered. Kwallek et al. concluded that introducing color to work environments to enhance productivity and mood might be difficult and risky as its impact is likely to vary from one employee to another:

Attempting to create the ideal environmental ambience through interior color across all individuals who may differ in several pertinent characteristics may be impossible. Alternatively interiors could be designed with maximum flexibility to allow for variation within the same general space according to each individual's relevant characteristics (p.131).

While Mahnke promotes color-in-workspace as a way of influencing employees' emotion, Kwallek et al. (1997) emphasizes individuating color selection to generate the desired emotional experience. Despite divergence in orientations, both studies acknowledge the power of color, as a design agent, to elicit individual emotions^{xi}. Further support is received from Schauss' (1985) study that found aggression to decrease in pink rooms. These findings align with recent research on *color as an emotional language* (Lechner & Harrington, 2005) centered on the premise that color carries a consistent set of meanings similar to any other linguistic instrument. In an empirical investigation of a U.S. based sample, subjects clearly associated emotions to colors in consistent ways leading the

researchers to propose that *color is a language of emotions*. In addition subjects identified color associations for what a color is and what it is not as shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1: Color as a Language of Emotions

Overall, research suggests that color influences subjects psychologically at an affective level (Birren, 1950; Goldstein, 1939), impacting how we feel and consequently, how we act (Birren, 1978). It is proposed that color as a design lever can be efficacious in promoting contexts for positive experience to enhance creativity and adaptation to change.

Where do we go from here? Concluding comments

So far we argued that an organizational life is saturated with emotions that accompany change and competitive pressures to create, innovate and differentiate. This organizational reality is stressful and emotionally difficult for people in organizations. We assumed the potential of workplace to offer a context of positive experience for its inhabitants in order to mitigate the negative impact of change while promoting positive experience to support creativity and adaptation. Along these lines others in the fields of design and business management acknowledge the importance of focusing on the experience that design creates:

Designing is one managerial activity that openly and enthusiastically includes emotion as a part of its process and as a part of its product. The emotional content of a design brings it a human meaning. It is the basis upon which people experience a design as being truly meaningful in their lives... a design without emotional content is dead and will not serve to enhance organizational performance (Boland and Collopy, 2004, p.270)

After a review of the various design levers that may be potent in creating contexts for *positive* experience, color seems to stand out as facilitator of emotions. At the same time, the color-emotion literature, presents an inconclusive view regarding color selection for particular desired emotional states, and for the most part it does not show *how* color is utilized to affect or support change in individuals. In particular, this literature is confused and thus confusing when addressing the *universality* of color impact. Specifically, it is unable to determine whether color in the workplace should be customized to support particular individual preferences, or support a universal palette, given that specific colors in this palette are known to promote innovative-creative thinking or other desired change goals. The notion that color cannot be uniformly associated with particular emotions, as Kwallek's study [1997] shows, makes the question of how color can be leveraged to affect contexts for desired positive experience a challenge that requires further research. We recognize that color-emotion theory, especially the subset that pertains to color and workplace, is in its infancy but also point to a consensus emerging about the potency of color in affecting the emotional states of individuals. Additional research is needed to better understand the universality of color's influence as well as its specific association to emotional states within the workplace.

Workplace design might act as a "persuasive artifact" (Latour, 1987) inviting people to engage in an experience, stimulate their interest and imagination, and facilitate and accommodate their contributions (Wagner, 2004). Its tremendous 'high-tech' support to organizations' innovation and adaptation to change needs can be complemented by its 'high-touch' impact (Domzal & Unger, 1987); its ability to generate context for positive emotional experience for individuals if we better understood how such emotional impact is generated and how exactly the emergent social reality is shaped assuming that:

The world of technological design is a solitary world of control and individual creation: a designer skillfully shapes available elements within his or her technical grasp into an architecture that

supports the desired functionality...this design world is driven by control, prediction and the omnipotent capability of the designer to make it fit with his anticipations. In the realm of language and social order, the situation is different. The world is not controlled, but co-created and negotiated...the issue which we often evade is: how can the designers design at all in the sense that we have defined above? Design in this context is not planned, sketched and anticipated – it emerges from our capability to enter into a dialogue with multiple communities and our capability to exercise power in front of forces that resist change” (Lyytinen, 2004:224)

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ⁱ While the term 'Emotion' enjoys multiple definitions and views (see for example the works of Plutchik, 1962, Farijda, 1986, Lazarus, 1991) we follow Farijda's, 1986 definition according to which emotions are tendencies to establish, maintain, or disrupt a relationship with the environment. Emotions might be defined as action readiness change in response to emergencies or interruptions

ⁱⁱ http://www.eiconsortium.org/research/business_case_for_ei.htm

ⁱⁱⁱ While the design literature celebrates and advances the design-emotion paradigm the term 'emotion' is problematic in that it is used too loosely or freely. The result is multiple conceptualizations of 'emotion' and little consensus regarding its definitionⁱⁱⁱ. In general, the literature on emotions is divided into two broad schools, highly heterogeneous in themselves, that debate whether to conceptualize emotions as anchored in dimensions (Wundt, 1924; Masson & McCarthy, 1995; Watson, 2000; Damasio, 1999; Johnston and Scherer, 2000; Cosmides and Tooby, 2000) or to see emotions as discrete categories (Lazarus, 1991; Plutchik, 1962, 2001). Despite this divergence, Plutchik rightfully points to some emergent consensus: emotions are usually triggered by one's interpretations of events; they involve strong reactions of many bodily systems; they communicate information from one person to another; and they help the individual adapt to changing environmental situations (Plutchik, 2003).

^{iv} While the design literature is not specific on its use of emotion terminology there is a reason to assume implicit attention to positive-negative typology.

^v Emotion typologies vary even within those who make a distinction between positive and negative similar to Fredrickson. For an elaborated review consult Plutchik, 2003

^{vi} The internationally respected architect, Sven Hesselgren coined the term 'emotional loading' to characterize an element of architectural design inherent in any interior or exterior environment. (In Mahnke, 1996, p.47)

^{vii} See for example the work of Hupka et al., 1997 and Terwogt & Hoeksma, 1999

^{viii} In the early days of the personal computer, all the display screens were black and white (...packaged in a gray plastic box - author's addition). When color screens were first introduced, I did not understand their popularity. In those days, color was primarily used either to highlight text or to add superfluous screen decoration. From a cognitive point of view, color added no value that could not be provided with the appropriate use of shading. But despite the fact that the interface community could find no scientific benefit, businesses insisted on buying color monitors. Obviously, color was fulfilling some need, but one we could not measure. In order to understand this phenomenon, I borrowed a color display to use with my computer. After the allocated time, I was convinced that my assessment had been correct -- color added no discernible value for everyday work. However, I refused to give up the color display. Although my reasoning told me that color was unimportant, my emotional reaction told me otherwise (Norman, 2002)

^{ix} Avery office products: Add some colour to your working life. June 25, 2004. PR Newswire Europe Limited

^x This finding was first contradicted by Stone who found just the opposite! (2001) and later further refined the research (Stone, 2003) and found that when performing a simple task performance appeared to deteriorate over time in the blue rather than red environment. Alternatively, working on a complex task performance appeared to deteriorate over time when working in a red rather than a blue environment. The researcher concludes that blue is a calming color and red an energizing one, that interact with other factors (such as task complexity) to affect performance (as an overall measurement of mood, motivation and task performance)

^{xi} Having said that we need to acknowledge that Stone (2001) found no effect of color in environment on motivation contrary to the work of Plack and Shick (1974) who suggested to use red and yellow in environment to motivate students.